

Absorption and Luminescence Investigation of 1-(2-Naphthyl)-2-(1-pyrrolidinyl) ethanone

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Abstract

Photoinitiators are the subject of extensive research due to their vital roles in photopolymerization. To examine the effectiveness of photoinitiators, it is required to determine their photophysical properties and the reaction rates of their excited states. Recently, 1-(2-Naphthyl)-2-(1-pyrrolidinyl) ethanone (MPY) as a type II photoinitiator has been synthesized and characterized. In this study, the effects of the solvent on the electronic absorption and fluorescence emission spectra of MPY were determined. The molar absorptivity values of MPY in several solvents with various polarities were calculated from the absorption spectra. Furthermore, singlet energies were obtained using the nearly mirror-image-like relationships between the excitation and emission spectra in different solvents.

Keywords: Solvent effects, photoinitiator, acetophenone, absorption spectrum, fluorescence spectrum, singlet energy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Photoinitiated free-radical polymerization reactions are extensively applied across various commercial sectors. The polymerization processes of acrylates and methacrylates initiated by light allow for the rapid fabrication of polymeric materials. Such materials find broad application in photoresist coatings, 3D printing and curing, imaging technologies, holographic data storage, and nanoscale micromechanical systems. The expansion of the photocuring industry relies on the ongoing innovation and enhancement of photoinitiated systems to satisfy industrial production requirements. Currently, a wide range of photoinitiated systems with diverse features—such as wavelength selectivity and high resolution—have been developed and are actively utilized in industrial applications [1-6].

Free radicals or ions are reactive species that initiate the polymerization of multifunctional monomers and oligomers are generated from photoinitiators. [7,8]. In free radical polymerization two types of photoinitiators are used: α -cleavable (Type I) and hydrogen abstraction type photoinitiators (Type II). Type I photoinitiators undergo α -cleavage during irradiation, producing two radical species. These initiators react with H-donor compounds such as tertiary amines, thiols, alcohols, and ethers in the triplet state, responsible for the formation of initiator radicals. Type II photoinitiators can be considered advantageous compared to Type I, because in most cases the energy required for bond cleavage of the photoinitiator is generally high and requires the use of short-wavelength, high-energy light sources [9-12].

To assess the efficiency of photoinitiators, it is crucial to investigate their photophysical characteristics along with the reaction kinetics of their excited states [13,14]. The electronic absorption and emission spectra of organic molecules are known to undergo significant alterations during solvation. In the liquid phase, spectrally active molecules often exhibit

variations in the frequency, intensity, or shape of their absorption and/or fluorescence spectra. Solvent-induced modifications in the electronic spectra of these molecules can yield valuable insights into the local electric field acting upon them. Typically, spectral shifts are attributed to specific solute–solute and solute–solvent interactions, such as hydrogen bonding or the collective properties of the solvent medium. In addition to these interactions, other factors—such as acid–base equilibria and charge-transfer processes—may also exert notable influences on the observed spectral behavior [15-17].

Recently, two photoinitiators, namely 2-morpholino acetone, 2-(N-methyl-N-phenylamino) acetone [18,19], 1-(naphthalen-2-yl)-2-(1H-pyrazol-1-yl) ethanone [20] and 4-methyl-4-[2-(naphthalen-2-yl)-2-oxoethyl] morpholin-4-ium iodide [21] have been synthesized and characterized. These α -cleavable initiators possess absorption properties in the UV region and can be effective for the polymerization of methyl methacrylate monomer. Another acetone derivative (MPY) was synthesized and characterized as a Type II photoinitiator [22]. In this study, the photophysical properties of MPY were investigated in different solvents using UV-visible and fluorescence spectroscopy.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Materials

N,N-dimethyl formamide, toluene, dichloromethane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, acetone, dimethyl sulfoxide, ethanol and methanol are supplied by Merck, and used as received.

2.2. Methods

Absorption spectra were measured with an Agilent Technologies 8453 spectrophotometer in the UV-visible region. Fluorescence spectra were obtained by using a Varian Eclipse spectrofluorometer at room temperature with 1 cm path length cuvettes.

2.3. Synthesis of (MPY)

MPY was synthesized, purified and characterized according to the procedure given in the literature [22].

Fig. 2.1. Structure of MPY.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Solvent Effects on Absorption Properties of MPY

In chemistry, solvents are qualitatively categorized as nonpolar, polar aprotic, and polar protic, and are typically ranked according to their dielectric constants. The dielectric constant, as defined by electrostatic principles, quantifies the interaction energy between two ions separated by a given distance. Protic solvents comprise molecules capable of donating hydrogen bonds, whereas aprotic solvents lack this ability. In general, polar solvents are characterized by high dielectric constants, while nonpolar (or apolar) solvents exhibit comparatively low dielectric constant values [13].

To investigate solvent effects on absorption properties of MPY, solvents are grouped into non-polar, polar aprotic and polar protic, and results are shown in Figures 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3. Molar absorptivity values are calculated for $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions from absorption spectra and compiled in Table 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Absorption spectra of MPY [6.17×10^{-5} M] in non-polar solvents.

Figure 3.2 Absorption spectra of MPY [6.17×10^{-5} M] in polar-protic solvents.

Figure 3.3 Absorption spectra of MPY [$6.17 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$] in polar-protic solvents.

The high stability (energy decrease) of non-bonding “n” orbitals is observed in polar solvents due to their polar structure. Similarly, π^* orbitals are more stable than π orbitals because π^* orbitals are more polar. Therefore, the reason for the shifts caused by solvent differentiation stems from the difference between the ability of solvent molecules to dissolve the excited state molecule and their ability to dissolve the ground state molecule [23].

Absorption spectra of MPY indicate that, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions express big differences according to solvent characteristics. As it can be seen from Table 3.1, the most proper solvents for $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions are Toluene > DMF > Ethanol and for $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions are Toluene > Ethanol > DMSO respectively.

Table 3.1 Molar absorptivity values of MPY in various solvents

Solvent	Dielectric constant	Molar absorptivity values	
Toluene	2.4	$\epsilon_{287} = -$	$\epsilon_{341} = 31174.9$
Chloroform	4.8	$\epsilon_{287} = 13926.7$	$\epsilon_{349} = 12850.9$
Dichloromethane	3.1	$\epsilon_{287} = 16826.4$	$\epsilon_{347} = 13827.9$
Ethyl acetate	6.0	$\epsilon_{280} = 18101.8$	$\epsilon_{340} = 13892.7$
Tetrahydrofuran	7.5	$\epsilon_{290} = 16619.4$	$\epsilon_{342} = 12508.1$
Acetone	21.0	$\epsilon_{297} = 6272.8$	$\epsilon_{344} = 16157.9$
Dimethyl formamide	38.0	$\epsilon_{291} = 32364.5$	$\epsilon_{350} = 25147.6$
Dimethyl sulfoxide	47.0	$\epsilon_{283} = 19659.8$	$\epsilon_{351} = 14962.4$
Ethanol	24.5	$\epsilon_{290} = 21854.2$	$\epsilon_{349} = 21227.9$
Methanol	33.0	$\epsilon_{287} = 15426.9$	$\epsilon_{351} = 14949.7$

Absorption band maxima are red shifted when the solvent polarity increases ($\lambda_{\text{CHLOROFORM}} = 349 \text{ nm} > \lambda_{\text{DCM}} = 347 \text{ nm} > \lambda_{\text{TOLUENE}} = 341 \text{ nm}$), ($\lambda_{\text{DMSO}} = 351 \text{ nm} > \lambda_{\text{DMF}} = 350 \text{ nm} > \lambda_{\text{ACETONE}} = 344 \text{ nm} > \lambda_{\text{THF}} = 342 \text{ nm} > \lambda_{\text{ETHYLACETATE}} = 340 \text{ nm}$), ($\lambda_{\text{METHANOL}} = 351 \text{ nm} > \lambda_{\text{ETHANOL}} = 349 \text{ nm}$). Furthermore, hyperchromic effect is observed with decreasing polarity ($\text{OD}_{\text{TOLUENE}} > \text{OD}_{\text{DCM}} > \text{OD}_{\text{CHLOROFORM}}$), ($\text{OD}_{\text{ETHANOL}} > \text{OD}_{\text{METHANOL}}$) (Figures 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3).

3.2. Fluorescence Study of MPY

Fluorescence emission spectra of MPY were measured in various solvents, to get more information on the nature of excited states of the photoinitiator. Solutions were excited at 300 nm and nearly mirror-image-like relations were observed between the excitation and emission spectra in dichloromethane, DMSO, ethanol and methanol (Figures 3.4, 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7). Fluorescence emission spectra of MPY dissolved in several solvents are depicted in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.4 Mirror image of normalized fluorescence excitation and emission of dichloromethane solution of MPY at room temperature ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm).

Figure 3.5 Mirror image of normalized fluorescence excitation and emission of DMSO solution of MPY at room temperature ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm).

Figure 3.6 Mirror image of normalized fluorescence excitation and emission of ethanol solution of MPY at room temperature ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm).

Figure 3.7 Mirror image of normalized fluorescence excitation and emission of methanol solution of MPY at room temperature ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm).

Figure 3.8 Fluorescence emission spectra of MPY ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm) in several solvents at room temperature.

A red shift was observed at fluorescence emission band maxima with decreasing solvent polarity ($\lambda_{DCM} = 442$ nm $>$ $\lambda_{ETHANOL} = 416$ nm $>$ $\lambda_{METHANOL} = 397$ nm \sim $\lambda_{DMF} = 400$ nm $>$ $\lambda_{DMSO} = 379$ nm). The biggest intensity value was obtained by methanol which is polar protic solvent. The singlet excited-state energy values of MPY were calculated from the intersection of the excitation-emission spectra and shown in Table 3.2. The lowest singlet energy of MPY is obtained by dichloromethane.

Table 3.2 Singlet energy values of MPY in different solvents

Solvent	Es (kJ/mol)
Dichloromethane (375 nm)	318.8
Dimethyl sulfoxide (361 nm)	331.2
Ethanol (363 nm)	329.4
Methanol (329)	363.4

4. CONCLUSIONS

Molar absorptivity values of MPY in different solvents from absorption spectra are calculated. For $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions; Toluene > DMF > Ethanol and for $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions; Toluene > Ethanol > DMSO are found to be most proper solvents. Nearly mirror-image-like relations were observed between the excitation and emission spectra in dichloromethane, DMSO, ethanol and methanol. A red shift was observed at fluorescence emission band maxima with decreasing solvent polarity. Besides, the biggest intensity value was obtained by methanol which is polar protic and the lowest singlet energy is obtained by dichloromethane which is a non-polar solvent.

Especially because of its high molar absorptivity value compared to other acetophenone derivatives, MPY can be used as an efficient photoinitiator in photopolymerization processes.

Authors contribution

SK.D.– conceptualization, investigation, data curation, writing original draft, funding acquisition; Z.D. – formal analysis, writing-review and editing.

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